

GENETICS AS A SCIENCE ABOUT INHERITANCE AND VARIATION PRINCIPLES. GENE LEVEL OF HEREDITARY MATERIAL ORGANIZATION IN PRO- AND EUKARYOTES.

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The genetics is a science about principles of heredity and diversity of organisms and about methods to direct them. The term "genetics" was suggested by English scientists W. Batson (from Greek 'geneticos' – related with birth). The heredity is an organisms property to transmit their traits and development features in line of following generations. Because of heredity, many species having been preserved unchanged during hundreds millions years (opossum, latimeria, gatteria). In sexual reproduction, a material basement of heredity is sperms and ovum, in asexual reproduction – somatic cells. The herediting is principles of hereditary traits transmitting process from one organism generation to another while reproduction. During sexual reproduction, herediting is performed through the sex cells, during asexual through the somatic cell division. The analysis of herediting principles is an important method to study heredity patterns. The genotype is integrity of all organism genes. The phenotype is integrity of all organism traits. It must be concerned that terms genotype and phenotype commonly are used in a narrow meaning. They may be related with such traits, which are interested for researcher at this moment. For example – white blue, dark or brown eyes in human. The diversity it is a variety of individual or group traits and properties. The diversity is a reflection of unstable preserving of individual hereditary information. It includes a gene changing and gene combining and changes in gene expression throughout individual development. The genetics studies heredity and diversity in four aspects. Firstly, it studies a problem of genetic information storage. It makes clear the material place of genetic information storage and the ways of genetic information coding.

Secondary, it studies a problem of genetic information transmitting and principles of that transmitting from cell to cell, from generation to generation. Thirdly, it analyzes a problem of genetic information realization. It studies how genetic information may be realized in definite traits of developing organism, in correspondence with external environment impacts. Fourthly, it considers the

problem of genetic information changing. It discovers the types and reasons of changing and mechanisms of its appearance.

There are following levels of hereditary information organization in pro- and eukaryotes: gene, chromosome and genome. The gene is a region of genomic nucleic acid, which is characterized by specific nucleotide sequence and which presents function unit different from other genes. The prokaryotic gene has unseparated DNA region. The eukaryotic have some fragments. These fragments may be exons (having useful information) and introns (without it). Introns are removed during gene expression (process of realization genetic information). Purposes of class: 1. To know particularities of hereditary material organization and mechanisms of gene expression regulation in pro- and eukaryotes. 2. To be able to solve problems on molecular genetics. 3. To be acquainted with achievements of gene engineering and biotechnology.

Literature:

1. Bekish V.J., Zorina V.V. Medical biology and general genetics. Textbook for students of educational establishments. Vitebsk: VSMU press, 2019. – p. 60–75.

